

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

Adaptation AGORA academy on climate data

Set of one-pagers

WP5– Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

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Adaptation AGORA academy on climate data

Premise: Under the capacity building activities, Adaptation AGORA has been developing different materials. They range from multimedia materials, like videos, recordings of webinars/conferences, to sets of slides, as well as content for the development of the two Academies. Adaptation AGORA is not responsible for the use of the materials (CC BY)

1. Link to the material: See annexes

2. Potential key entries to search material.

Category and Target: Category: Capacity building, Climate Data; Target: University students, general public, NGOs, journalists, public authorities

3. Brief Introduction/Summary

Estimated time: 35min

Objective: Overview of the Academy on Climate Data and its use

Type of resource: Set of slides

Language: English

4. Key Challenges/ issues addressed

- What are the main barriers and limitations of existing climate platforms and tools?
- How should the Digital Academies encourage stakeholders and citizens to engage and actively participate with the platforms?
- How can the Digital Academies facilitate learning and access to materials?

5. What the Resource Offers

Overview on what the Academy of climate data is and its structure, how the resource can be used in co-design processes.

Adaptation AGORA akadeemia kliimaandmed

Adaptation AGORA on võimekuse suurendamise eesmärgil välja töötanud erinevaid materjale, nt nagu multimeediasisu (videod, veebiseminaride/konverentside salvestused), slaidikomplektide, samuti kahe akadeemia arendamiseks mõeldud sisu. Adaptation Agora ei vastuta materjalide kasutamise eest (CC BY).

1. **Link materjalile:** Vt lisad

2. **Võimalikud märksõnad materjali otsimiseks.**

Kategooria ja sihtrühm: Kategooria: võimekuse suurendamine, kliimaandmed; Sihtrühm: üliõpilased, laiem üldsus, valitsusvälised organisatsioonid, ajakirjanikud, riigiasutused

3. **Lühike sissejuhatus/kokkuvõte**

Hinnanguline kestus: 35min

Eesmärk: Ülevaade kliimaandmete akadeemiast ja selle kasutamisest

Ressursi tüüp: Slaidide komplekt

Keel: inglise keel

4. **Peamised väljakutsed/ lahendatavad probleemid**

- Millised on olemasolevate kliimaplatvormide ja -vahendite peamised takistused ja piirangud?
- Kuidas peaksid digitaalakadeemiad julgustama sidusrühmi ja kodanikke platvormidega suhtlema ja neis aktiivselt osalema?
- Kuidas saavad digitaalakadeemiad hõlbustada õppimist ja juurdepääsu materjalidele?

5. **Mida ressurss pakub?**

Ülevaade kliimaandmete akadeemia olemusest ja struktuurist, kuidas seda ressursi saab ühise disaini protsessides kasutada.

Académie AGORA sur l'adaptation aux données climatiques

Dans le cadre des activités de renforcement des capacités, Adaptation AGORA a développé différents supports. Ceux-ci incluent des contenus multimédias (vidéos, enregistrements de webinaires ou de conférences, ensembles de diapositives), ainsi que des supports pour le développement de deux Académies. L'utilisation de ces contenus, mis à disposition sous licence Creative Commons (CC BY), relève de la responsabilité des utilisateurs et non du projet Adaptation Agora.

1. Lien vers le contenu : voir annexes

2. Entrées clés potentielles pour rechercher du matériel :

Catégorie : Renforcement des capacités, données climatiques

Cible : étudiants universitaires, grand public, ONG, journalistes, autorités publiques

3. Brève introduction / résumé :

- Temps estimé : 35 min
- Objectif : présenter l'Académie sur les données climatiques et son utilisation
- Type de ressource : présentation PowerPoint (ppt)
- Langue : anglais

4. Principaux défis abordés :

- Quels sont les principaux obstacles et limites des plateformes et outils climatiques actuellement disponibles ?
- Comment les académies numériques peuvent-elles encourager les parties prenantes et les citoyens à s'engager et à participer activement aux plateformes ?
- Comment les académies numériques peuvent-elles faciliter l'apprentissage et l'accès aux ressources ?

5. Apports de la ressource :

Présentation générale de l'Académie des données climatiques, de sa structure et de la manière dont cette ressource peut être utilisée dans les processus de co-conception.

AGORA-Akademie zu Klimadaten

Im Rahmen der "Hilfe zur Selbsthilfe" - Aktivitäten hat das Projekt Adaptation AGORA verschiedene Ressourcen entwickelt. Dies beinhaltet multimediale Inhalte wie Videos, Aufzeichnungen von Webinaren/Konferenzen, Foliensätze sowie Inhalte für die Entwicklung der beiden Online-Akademien. Adaptation AGORA ist nicht verantwortlich für die Nutzung der Ressourcen (CC BY).

1. Link zur Ressource: siehe Anhang

2. Potenzielle Suchbegriffe:

Kategorie und Zielgruppe: Kategorie: Kapazitätsaufbau, Klimadaten; Zielgruppe: Studierende, allgemeine Öffentlichkeit, Nichtregierungsorganisationen, Journalist*innen, Behörden

3. Kurze Einführung/Zusammenfassung

Geschätzte Zeit: 35min

Ziel: Überblick über die Akademie für Klimadaten und ihre Nutzung

Ressourcentyp: Folien-Set

Sprache: Englisch

4. Zentrale Herausforderungen/Probleme, die adressiert werden

- Was sind die größten Hindernisse und Einschränkungen bestehender Klimaplattformen und -instrumente?
- Wie sollten die Digital Academies Stakeholder und Bürger*innen dazu ermutigen, sich zu engagieren und aktiv die Plattformen zu nutzen?
- Wie können die Digital Academies das Lernen und den Zugang zu Materialien erleichtern?

5. Was die Ressource bietet

Überblick darüber, was die Akademie zu Klimadaten ist, ihre Struktur und wie diese Ressourcen in Ko-Kreationsprozessen genutzt werden kann

Ακαδημία Adaptation AGORA για τα κλιματικά δεδομένα

Σημείωση: Στο πλαίσιο των δραστηριοτήτων ανάπτυξης ικανοτήτων, το πρόγραμμα Adaptation AGORA έχει δημιουργήσει επιμορφωτικό και εκπαιδευτικό υλικό. Αυτό περιλαμβάνει πολυμεσικό υλικό, όπως βίντεο, μαγνητοσκοπημένα διαδικτυακά σεμινάρια/συνεδρία, παρουσιάσεις, καθώς και το περιεχόμενο που χρησιμοποιήθηκε για την ανάπτυξη των δύο διαδικτυακών Ακαδημιών. Το Adaptation Agora δεν φέρει ευθύνη για τη χρήση των υλικών (CC BY).

1. Σύνδεσμος προς το υλικό: βλέπε παραρτήματα

2. Πιθανοί βασικοί όροι αναζήτησης του υλικού.

Κατηγορία: Ανάπτυξη ικανοτήτων, Κλιματικά δεδομένα

Ομάδες-στόχοι: Φοιτητές πανεπιστημίου, κοινό, ΜΚΟ, δημοσιογράφοι, δημόσιες αρχές

3. Σύντομη εισαγωγή/περίληψη

Εκτιμώμενος χρόνος: 35 λεπτά

Σκοπός: Επισκόπηση της Ακαδημίας για τα Κλιματικά Δεδομένα και τη χρήση της

Τύπος υλικού: Σειρά διαφανειών

Γλώσσα: Αγγλικά

4. Βασικές προκλήσεις/ζητήματα που αντιμετωπίζονται

- Ποια είναι τα κύρια εμπόδια και οι περιορισμοί των υφιστάμενων πλατφορμών και εργαλείων για το κλίμα;
- Πώς πρέπει οι Διαδικτυακές Ακαδημίες να ενθαρρύνουν τους ενδιαφερόμενους φορείς και τους πολίτες να εμπλακούν και να συμμετάσχουν ενεργά με τις πλατφόρμες ασύγχρονης μάθησης;
- Πώς μπορούν οι Διαδικτυακές Ακαδημίες να διευκολύνουν τη μάθηση και την πρόσβαση σε υλικό;

5. Τι προσφέρει το επιμορφωτικό υλικό

Επισκόπηση της Ακαδημίας για τα κλιματικά δεδομένα και της δομής της, καθώς και του τρόπου με τον οποίο ο πόρος μπορεί να χρησιμοποιηθεί σε διαδικασίες συν-σχεδιασμού.

Accademia digitale sui dati climatici - Adaptation AGORA

Nell'ambito delle attività di capacity building, Adaptation AGORA ha sviluppato diversi materiali che spaziano da contenuti multimediali, come video e registrazioni di webinar/conferenze, presentazioni in power point, nonché contenuti per lo sviluppo delle due Accademie. Adaptation Agora non è responsabile dell'utilizzo dei materiali (CC BY)

1. Link Alla risorsa: vedi allegati

2. Parole chiave per cercare la risorsa:

Categoria: rafforzamento delle competenze, dati climatici

Destinatari: pubblico generale, studenti universitari, NGO, giornalisti, autorità pubbliche

3. Sintesi:

Tempo stimato per la consultazione della risorsa: 35min

Obiettivo: panoramica generale dell'Accademia sui dati climatici e suo utilizzo

Tipo di risorsa: presentazione power point

Lingua: Inglese

4. Principali sfide/problematiche affrontate:

- Quali sono i principali ostacoli e limiti delle attuali piattaforme e strumenti sul clima?
- In che modo le Accademie Digitali dovrebbero incentivare il coinvolgimento attivo di stakeholder e cittadini con le piattaforme?
- Come possono le Accademie Digitali facilitare l'apprendimento e l'accesso ai materiali?

5. Cosa offre la risorsa:

Panoramica su cos'è l'Accademia sui Dati Climatici e sulla sua struttura, e su come la risorsa possa essere utilizzata nei processi di co-progettazione.

Academia sobre datos climáticos de Adaptation AGORA

En el marco de las actividades de desarrollo de capacidades, Adaptation AGORA ha elaborado diversos materiales. Estos abarcan desde materiales multimedia, como vídeos y grabaciones de seminarios web y conferencias, hasta conjuntos de diapositivas, así como contenidos para el desarrollo de las dos academias. Adaptation Agora no se hace responsable del uso de los materiales (CC BY).

1. Enlace al material: Ver anexos

2. Posibles entradas clave para buscar el material:

Categoría: Desarrollo de capacidades, datos climáticos

Target: Estudiantes universitarios, público en general, ONG, periodistas, autoridades públicas

3. Breve introducción/resumen:

Tiempo estimado: 35min

Objetivo: Descripción general de la Academia sobre datos climáticos y su uso

Tipo de recurso: Conjunto de diapositivas

Idioma: Inglés

4. Retos clave/temas abordados:

- ¿Cuáles son las principales barreras y limitaciones de las plataformas y herramientas climáticas existentes?
- ¿Cómo deben las Academias Digitales animar a las partes interesadas y a los ciudadanos a comprometerse y participar activamente en las plataformas?
- ¿Cómo pueden las Academias Digitales facilitar el aprendizaje y el acceso a los materiales?

5. Qué ofrece el recurso:

Descripción general de qué es la Academia de datos climáticos y su estructura, cómo se puede utilizar el recurso en los procesos de diseño conjunto.

Adaptation AGORA Academy: Klimatdata

Adaptation AGORA har tagit fram olika material för kapacitetsutveckling. Dessa inkluderar allt från multimediamaterial, såsom videor och inspelningar av webbseminarier och konferenser, till bildsamlingar och material för utvecklingen av de två akademierna. Adaptation AGORA ansvarar inte för hur materialen används (CC BY).

1. Länk till materialet: Se bilagor

2. Potentiella sökord. Kategori och målgrupp:

Kategori: Kapacitetsutveckling, Klimatdata; Målgrupp: Universitetsstuderande, allmänheten, icke-statliga organisationer, journalister, myndigheter

3. Kort introduktion/sammanfattning

Beräknad tid: 35min

Syfte: Översikt över Akademin för klimatdata och dess tillämpningar

Typ av resurs: Bildsamling

Språk: Engelska

4. Centrala umaningar/problem som behandlas

- Vilka är de främsta hindren och begränsningarna för befintliga klimatplattformar och verktyg?
- Hur kan digitala akademier främja engagemang och deltagande bland invånare?
- På vilket sätt kan digitala akademier underlätta lärande och förbättra tillgången till material?

5. Vad resursen erbjuder

Översikt över Akademin, dess struktur, och hur den kan användas i gemensamma utformningsprocesser.

Annex: Resource

Funded by the European Union

EU MISSIONS
ADAPTATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE

Adaptation AGORA is a HORIZON Europe 3-years project started in January 2023 and coordinated by the CMCC Foundation.

Aligning with the overall goals of the EU Mission on Climate Change Adaptation, AGORA project:

- promotes **social transformation processes** in diverse contexts through transdisciplinary tools and approaches;
- encourages **effective engagement of citizens and communities in actions against climate change**;
- accelerates the local adaptation processes to build a Europe resilient to climate change.

Digital Academies in Adaptation AGORA

Digital Academy to access and use Climate Data and monitor Climate Risks

This Digital Academy aims to:

- Identify, provide access to, and share guidance on how to use various open source climate and risk data
- Provide easy access to information
- Empower citizens, stakeholders, and policy makers
- Enhance the visualisation of climate information

Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation

This Digital Academy aims to provide access to:

- Trustworthy information
- Fact-checked reports and documents
- Relevant and emerging resources
- Bi-annual reports

Co-design event for the Digital Academy: ECCA2023

Q1: What are the **main barriers and limitations** of existing climate platforms and tools enabling the use of climate information?

- lack of understanding
- knowledge gaps and lack of training
- complexity of the data and a lack of trust
- lack of dissemination of the existing platforms

Q2: How should the Digital Academies **encourage stakeholders and citizens to engage and actively participate with the platforms?**

- mapping the target groups
- encouraging stakeholder and citizen dialogue from the beginning
- making the DA funny, entertaining, attractive, user friendly
- showcasing examples, sharing needs and solutions

45-50 attender

Q3: How can the Digital Academies **facilitate learning and access to materials?**

- remaining current and updated
- making it clear, actionable, with intuitive interface, simple language, and videos, pictures and stories
- promoting open/free access to downloadable materials
- fostering the visualization
- demonstrating the relevance, usability, and legitimacy

Co-development process for the Digital Academy: SISC2023

Exploring the Digital Academy

<https://agoradigitalacademy.dataclime.com/>

The three pillars of the Digital Academy

Inventories select and gather existing hubs and platforms on:

CLIMATE
DATA

CLIMATE
RISKS

CLIMATE
ADAPTATION

The inventories provide climate data, derived climate information on climate risk and adaptation, sector- or user-specified climate services to a large range of users. These inventories aim to enhance knowledge, raise awareness, and inspire collective action to cope with climate change.

The three pillars of the Digital Academy

The AGORA Digital Academy supports users with learning modules on how to read, interpret and effectively use climate-related information.

EIGHT
MODULES

Modules provide a general overview to inform about climate change, models, tools, risk assessment, governance, policies, adaptation and new frontiers.

The three pillars of the Digital Academy

As the AGORA Digital Academy is designed as a living tool, citizens can highlight existing initiatives and good practices at local and European levels to guide and inspire other communities on how to tackle climate-related risks.

CITIZEN
SCIENCE FORM

Citizens can actively collaborate with AGORA researchers compiling a form to:

- > Highlight the existence of climate local data
- > Inform about local initiatives

How a Module is composed?

Title:

Overview: (length of the module, description of the narrative; presentation of exercises and of the videos. What a learner can view/train/learn?)

Instructors: (brief CV of instructors in charge of the module)

Overview Live Session: (2 or 3 minutes length video presenting the overview of the module and the instructors)

Topics:

Objectives:

Skill level: (BASE / INTERMEDIATE / ADVANCED)

Roadmap: (hypertextual narrative with links to shot existing videos (as CDS, other EU projects) to easily support the learner)

Quizzes or questionnaires: (5 or 6 questions for module)

Video or tutorial: (practical exercises on the specific topics showing "how to do", "excel or python script", tutorial on how to use inventories)

References and peer-reviewed papers: (list of sources and referred papers suggested for interested people)

Skill levels

BASE	1. WHAT IS CLIMATE?
INTERMEDIATE	2. HOW CAN CLIMATE MODELS BENEFIT YOU?
BASE	3. HOW TO USE AND VISUALIZE CLIMATE DATA?
INTERMEDIATE	4. CLIMATE THREATS AND HAZARDS
INTERMEDIATE	5. CLIMATE RISKS
BASE	6. MITIGATION, ADAPTATION & GOVERNANCE
BASE	7. INVESTIGATE OPTIONS AND TAKE ACTIONS!
ADVANCED	8. NEW FRONTIERS

Example: Module 1

Title: WHAT IS CLIMATE? (<https://agoradigitalacademy.dataclimate.com/courses/entry-level/>)

Duration: 30 minutes

Instructors: Marianna Adinolfi, Madeline Baldelli

Topics: Climate and Weather, Climate change, IPCC, social aspect of climate change

Brief overview: The module aims to deepen learners' understanding of climate by exploring its various aspects, including the differences between climate and weather, evidences of global warming, the social impacts of climate change and the role of international organizations like IPCC and COP.

Skill level: BASE

Roadmap: hypertextual narrative with links to shot existing videos and papers from ESA, NOAA, IPCC or educational videos on YouTube about the key topics of the module to easily support the learner (20 minutes)

Quizzes or questionnaires: 8 questions about key takeaways messages, enhancing users' fundamental knowledge of essential climate concepts (10 minutes)

Video or tutorial: educational videos about key topics like "[Climate Change: How does it really work?](#)", "[Introducing the IPCC – Interactive Atlas](#)"

References and peer-reviewed papers:

- Hawkins, E. & Sutton, R., 2011: Il potenziale per restringere l'incertezza nelle proiezioni del cambiamento delle precipitazioni regionali. *Clim. Dynam.* 37, 407–418.
- Lenton, TM, Xu, C., Abrams, JF, Ghadiali, A., Loriani, S., Sakschewski, B., ... & Scheffer, M. (2023). Quantificazione del costo umano del riscaldamento globale. *Nature Sustainability*, 6 (10), 1237-1247.

